

Mechanism of Iridium(III) catalysed Oxidation of Valeric Acid by *N*-Bromoacetamide

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Kinetics of oxidation of valeric acid by *N*-bromoacetamide have been studied in the presence of acidic solution of Ir^{III}. A first order dependence with respect to *N*-bromoacetamide and Ir^{III} has been observed. Valeric acid exhibits zero order kinetics. Negative effect of acetamide and hydrogen ions while positive effect of mercuric acetate variation were observed. A general mechanism consistent with the above observations had been proposed.

N-Bromoacetamide has been used as oxidising agent^{1,2} for a number of primary alcohols, amino acids, dimethyl sulphide and ketones, but so far none has attempted to probe the catalytic potential of Ir^{III} in NBA oxidation of the valeric acid in acidic medium in presence of mercuric acetate. So effort has been made to collect the kinetic data and use them for elucidating the oxidation paths with special reference to catalytic activity of Ir^{III} in perchloric acid.

Experimental

The standard solutions of valeric and perchloric acids (E. Merck, G.R.) were directly prepared in double-distilled water. An aqueous solution of NBA (E. Merck, G.R.) was prepared afresh and standardised by estimating its bromine iodometrically. Solution of mercuric acetate (E. Merck) was prepared in acetic acid and that of iridium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) in hydrochloric acid.

The reaction mixture was prepared by mixing the requisite amount of reducing substrate, perchloric acid, mercuric acetate and all other reagents except for *N*-bromoacetamide (NBA) and was maintained at a desired temperature. The initiation of reaction was carried out by mixing appropriate volume of NBA (also kept at the same temperature in a separate flask) with reaction mixture. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating remaining amount of NBA iodometrically at different time intervals.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the effect of variation of NBA on the rate of reaction, where it is clear that the values of the first order rate constant, k_{obs} (calculated by the formula, $k_{obs} = (-dc/dt)/[NBA]$) remain constant at different [NBA], indicating first order with respect to NBA. Further, no significant change in

k_{obs} was observed with an increase in initial concentration of valeric acid, which indicates zero order dependence of the reaction on the concentration of valeric acid (Table 1). A linear relationship between k_{obs} values and [Ir^{III}] holds good (Table 2), showing first order dependence of the reaction in [Ir^{III}]. It is obvious from the Table 3 that on increasing perchloric acid concentration, the value of k_{obs} decreases showing negative effect of hydrogen ions. The above observation is also clear from the straightline plot between k_{obs} and $1/[H^+]$ (not shown).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [NBA] AND [VALERIC ACID] ON REACTION RATE

[HClO₄] = 1.00 × 10⁻² M, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 2.50 × 10⁻³ M, [Ir^{III}] = 4.52 × 10⁻⁵ M
[KCl] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M, μ = 1.75 × 10⁻² M Temp. = 35°

[Valeric acid] 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M		[NBA] 1.25 × 10 ⁻³ M	
[NBA] × 10 ⁴ M	k_{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	[Valeric acid] M	k_{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.72	4.22	1.00	3.37
0.83	4.00	1.50	3.40
1.25	3.37	2.00	3.42
1.40	3.39	3.00	3.38
1.60	3.05	4.00	3.35
1.80	3.63	5.00	3.36

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [Ir^{III}] ON REACTION RATE*

[Valeric acid] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M, [HClO₄] = 0.50 × 10⁻² M, [NBA] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 2.50 × 10⁻³ M, [KCl] = 1.00 × 10⁻² M, μ = 2.25 × 10⁻² M, Temp. = 35°

[Ir ^{III}] × 10 ⁶ M	k_{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k_2 × 10 ⁸ mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹
5.66	1.00	1.76
11.32	2.42	2.13
16.90	2.77	1.63
22.60	3.46	1.53
33.90	5.00	1.47
45.20	7.02	1.55

where $k_2 = k_{obs}/[Ir^{III}]$

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF [H⁺] ON REACTION RATE

[Valeric acid]=1.00×10⁻³ M, [NBA]=1.00×10⁻² M,
[Hg(OAc)₂]=2.50×10⁻² M, [Ir^{III}]=4.52×10⁻⁶ M,
[KCl]=1.00×10⁻² M, μ=3.5×10⁻² M, Temp.=35°

[HClO ₄] × 10 ² M	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.12	8.97
0.16	7.77
0.40	6.83
0.66	6.25
1.00	3.97
1.40	3.58
1.60	3.06

Table 4 contains the kinetic results obtained at different concentrations of mercuric acetate, acetamide and at various ionic strengths of the medium. The rate increases with increase in [Hg(OAc)₂] indicating positive effect of mercuric acetate. This confirms the role of mercuric acetate as catalyst. Retarding effect of acetamide was observed while positive effect of ionic strength was evident. It is clear from the straightline plot of 1/k_{obs} vs [KCl] (not shown) that the rate of reaction decreases with the increase in concentration of chloride ions.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF ADDITION OF MERCURIC ACETATE, ACETAMIDE AND IONIC STRENGTH VARIATION ON REACTION RATE

[Valeric acid]=1.00×10⁻³ M, [HClO₄]=1.00×10⁻² M,
[NBA]=0.83×10⁻² M, [Ir^{III}]=11.32×10⁻⁵ M,
[KCl]=1.00×10⁻² M, μ=3.50×10⁻² M (unless otherwise stated), Temp.=35°

[Hg(OAc) ₂] × 10 ³ M	k _{obs} * × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.80	3.48
1.00	5.64
1.60	7.38
2.50	10.70
5.00	15.80
0.75	3.12 ^a
0.75	3.32 ^b
0.75	2.91 ^c
0.75	2.86 ^d
0.75	2.50 ^e
1.00	5.71 ^f
1.00	5.92 ^g
1.00	6.56 ^h

*[Acetamide]=^a0.20, ^b0.28, ^c0.40, ^d0.66 and ^e1.0×10⁻² M.
Ionic strength (μ)=^f2.50, ^g3.00, ^h5.00×10⁻² M.

Mercuric acetate has been used as a scavenger for bromide ions produced in the reaction in order to eliminate parallel oxidation by Br₂ which is formed as a result of interaction between Br⁻ and N-bromoacetamide. Hence in order to ensure oxidation purely by NBA, Br⁻ ions are scavenged by mercuric acetate².

In acidic media, NBA is reported³ to exist in the following two sets of equilibria (1, 2) and (3, 4) which are kinetically indistinguishable in the present case.

OR

Thus from the above equilibria it seems that there can be four reactive species of NBA, namely, NBA, HOBr, protonated NBA (NB⁺AH) and H₂O⁺Br (cationic bromine). Experimentally observed negative effect of hydrogen ions cannot be explained on assuming either NBA or protonated NBA as a active species involved in the present investigations. Hence these cannot be the reactive species in the above reaction. Similarly required first order in hydrogen ions, contrary to observed negative effect, does not allow us to assume H₂OBr⁺ as active species. Hence involvement of H₂OBr⁺ as active species of NBA is also ruled out. Now the only choice left is to assume HOBr as active species of NBA. It shows negative effect of acetamide and hydrogen ions as well. Thus HOBr in all probability is safely assumed to be the most reactive species of NBA in acidic media.

In view of negative effect of chloride ions, [IrCl₆(H₂O)]²⁻ can be taken as the actual reactive species⁴ of Ir^{III} chloride in acidic media.

Now on the basis of above discussion, the following reaction steps are suggested,

where S is valeric acid. Considering the above steps, the rate of reaction in terms of disappearance of NBA may be written as equation (5),

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBA}]}{dt} = \frac{k_a K_1 K_2 K_3 K_4 [\text{NBA}][\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}][\text{Hg}^{\text{II}}]}{[\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-](k_{-1}[\text{NBH}] + k_2[\text{Hg}^{\text{II}}])} \quad (5)$$

where K₁=(k₁/k₋₁) and K₂=(k₂/k₋₂). The rate law (5) clearly shows first order kinetics in [NBA]

and $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ and inverse first order in $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$. Experimentally observed deviation from inverse first order in $[\text{H}^+]$ is ascribed to the formation of unreactive protonated HOBr (i.e. H_2OBr^+) and protonated NBA, (i.e. $\text{CH}_3\text{CON}^+\text{H}_2\text{Br}$) species. Similarly, deviation from inverse first order in $[\text{Cl}^-]$ is due to the formation of unreactive $[\text{IrCl}_6]^{3-}$ species on successive addition of Cl^- ions. Positive effect of Hg^{II} (straight line plot between $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Hg}^+]$ not shown) and negative effect of acetamide (NBH) are also explained by rate law (5).

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